
229. RR Lyrae variables: an update

I DESCRIBED Gaia's early contributions to the study of RR Lyrae variables in essay 45, where I included an introduction to their nature and importance. Essay 43 was written at the end of 2021, before Data Release 3. Before bringing the topic up-to-date, let me recall the state of knowledge at that time, about three years ago.

GIVEN THEIR long lifetimes, stars of approximately solar mass are still present in old Population II systems, including globular clusters. After ascending the giant branch, terminating in the helium flash, they evolve rapidly onto the 'zero-age horizontal branch' with masses around $0.6 - 0.8 M_{\odot}$, where they basically comprise a static He-burning core and a H-burning shell.

RR Lyrae are a subset of the horizontal branch giants, occurring where the horizontal branch intersects the instability strip (e.g. Catelan, 2009). They have pulsation periods around 1 day or less. Like Cepheids, although less luminous, their distinctive light curves allows detection to large distances, as far as the Galactic centre in the low-absorption Baade Windows, and in crowded fields.

The RRab subgroup, most relevant to the distance scale, are metal-poor spheroidal component stars, with asymmetric light curves, longer periods (above 0.4 day), larger amplitudes (around 0.5–1.5 mag), and pulsating in the fundamental mode. The less numerous RRc type are old disk component stars, with more symmetric almost sinusoidal light curves, shorter periods (below 0.4 day), smaller variability amplitudes, and pulsating in the first overtone. There are also double-mode pulsators, denoted RRd, which pulsate simultaneously in the fundamental mode and in the first overtone. I say more on the origin of this nomenclature in essay 230.

An underlying period–luminosity relation has long given RR Lyrae stars a role as standard candles for relatively nearby targets, especially within the Milky Way and Local Group. Although more common than Cepheids, there are greater difficulties in accounting for the effects of metallicity, faintness, and blending. As for the Cepheids, they also provide tests of evolutionary and pulsation models, and are important kinematic tracers.

THEIR TYPICALLY large distances means that trigonometric parallaxes have largely been unavailable in the past, and various other less-direct methods have been used for luminosity calibration. Pre-Gaia, several thousand Galactic RR Lyrae stars were known. But because of their magnitudes, only 179 were observed by Hipparcos. And it eventually gave useful parallaxes for only a few, with only the class's prototype, RR Lyrae itself at $\pi = 4.38 \pm 0.59$ milli-arcsec, being reasonably accurate.

THE HIGH-ACCURACY parallaxes from Gaia, combined with its multi-colour multi-epoch precision photometry, makes the mission extremely powerful for identifying and characterising variability across the entire HR diagram. The first Gaia data release, DR1, included 2595 RR Lyrae stars in the Large Magellanic Cloud region, which was observed at high cadence during the first 28 days in the 'ecliptic poles scanning configuration' (Clementini et al., 2016).

For Gaia DR2, covering the first 22 months of mission data, a 'Specific Object Study' pipeline was used to validate and characterise both Cepheids and RR Lyrae stars, originally using the period–amplitude and period–luminosity relations only in the *G* band, and subsequently extended to G_{BP} and G_{RP} (Clementini et al., 2019; Rimoldini et al., 2019). Gaia DR2 accordingly provided astrometric and photometric results, including mean magnitudes and pulsation characteristics, for 140 784 RR Lyrae stars as faint as $G = 20.7$ mag, of which some 50 000 were new discoveries.

This huge sample includes objects in the Milky Way disk, bulge, and halo; in the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds; 1569 distributed over 87 globular clusters; and 417 distributed over 12 dwarf spheroidal galaxies (including seven ultra-faint dwarf galaxies). The largest numbers are in M3 (159), NGC 3201 (83), Sculptor (176) and Draco (176).

The accurate multi-epoch photometry resulted in 121 234 objects whose light curves could be modelled with at least two harmonics, and 67 681 modelled with at least three harmonics.

FOR THE 83 097 stars with both G_{BP} and G_{RP} photometry, the colour–magnitude diagram shows the different regions occupied by the RRab, RRc, and RRd classes, along with clumps associated with the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds, as well as the Draco and Sculptor dwarf spheroidals (Clementini et al., 2019, Figure 15).

As detailed in essay 45, the DR2 sample was used for improved period–luminosity–metallicity relations (e.g. Neeley et al., 2017; Neeley et al., 2019; Muraveva et al., 2018), and to probe the triaxial structure, kinematics, and accretion history of the Galaxy halo (e.g. Utkin et al., 2018; Iorio et al., 2018; Iorio & Belokurov, 2019).

RR Lyrae stars found well beyond a system’s tidal radius provide evidence for tidal disruption, both for Galactic globular clusters (Kundu et al., 2019), and ultra-faint dwarf satellite galaxies (Vivas et al., 2020). Some 6000–11 000 have been associated with the Sagittarius tidal stream (Ramos et al., 2020), others with the Gaia–Enceladus stream (Prudil et al., 2020), and some 15 000 with the Milky Way’s central bulge (Du et al., 2020).

GAIA DR3 brought a wealth of new astrometric and photometric information. As for the Cepheids (essay 228), specific processing of the RR Lyrae again used the (updated) ‘Specific Object Study’ Cepheid/RR Lyrae pipeline (Clementini et al., 2023). This included analysis of the Gaia three-colour (G , BP, RP) time-series photometry, along with the epoch radial velocities (available for 1096). From 271 779 initial candidates, a high-quality sample of 270 905 RR Lyrae stars was constructed (of which 70 611 are new discoveries), comprising 174 947 fundamental-mode (RRab), 93 952 first-overtone (RRc), and 2006 double-mode (RRd) pulsators.

The sample includes RR Lyrae in 95 globular clusters and 25 Milky Way companions (the Magellanic Clouds, seven dwarf spheroidal galaxies, and 16 ultra-faint dwarf satellites). The catalogue includes an estimate of the interstellar absorption for 142 660 fundamental-mode pulsators (based on the G -band amplitude, the $G - G_{RP}$ colour, and the pulsation period). Metallicities, derived from the Fourier parameters of the light curves, are included for 133 559 objects. Further analyses include independent metallicity estimates (Jurcsik & Hajdu, 2023), leading to individual metallicities and distances for 134 000, as well as mean metallicities and distances to the LMC/SMC, and to 38 Milky Way globular clusters (Muraveva et al., 2025).

Further studies of the period–luminosity–metallicity relations have followed (Bhardwaj et al., 2023; Mullen et al., 2023; Zgirski et al., 2023), which I will not attempt to synthesise. The Gaia DR3 samples have also been used for new calibrations of the Baade–Wesselink (or parallax-of-pulsation) technique, based on a comparison of the variation of the star’s linear radius and its angular diameter (Bras et al., 2024; Zgirski et al., 2024).

APPLICATION OF THE enlarged DR3 sample to studies of Galactic structure have also continued. These include determination of the distance and dynamics of the bulge region (Prudil et al., 2024a; Prudil et al., 2024b; Kunder et al., 2024; Prudil et al., 2025), and the structure and rotation of the inner and outer halo (Culpan et al., 2024; Cabrera Garcia et al., 2024; Tkachenko et al., 2024). The possible accretion origin for some of them provides support to the idea that the accretion of sub-haloes largely contributes to the outer halo stellar populations (Medina et al., 2023).

The DR3 RR Lyrae sample also provides an important probe of the recently-identified (and various unidentified) Galactic phase-space sub-structures (Sun et al., 2025). From 46 575 of the halo stars (and using a Gaussian prior for the radial velocities), their friends-of-friends algorithm successfully identifies groups moving along similar orbits, amongst which are the Sagittarius stream, the Hercules–Aquila Cloud (HAC), the Virgo Overdensity (VOD), the Gaia Enceladus–Sausage (GES), various other halo streams (Orphan–Chenab, Cetus–Palca, Helmi, Sequoia, and Wukong), as well as the LMC leading arm, and another 18 unknown groups.

AN INDEPENDENT CATALOGUE of 2824 RR Lyrae stars in 115 Galactic globular clusters (including 1594 fundamental-mode, 824 first-overtone, and 28 double-mode pulsators) has been given by Cruz Reyes et al. (2024). They found that 77% of the known RR Lyrae stars in globular clusters are included in the Gaia DR3 Specific Object Study, with 82% being correctly classified. The majority of the missing sources are located in the crowded cluster centres.

Although they found that 80% of RRab, 84% of RRc, and 100% of the RRd pulsators are located within theoretical instability strip boundaries predicted using MESA models (with metallicity $Z=0.0003$, mass $M = 0.7M_{\odot}$, and helium $Y=0.290$), they also found that 25% of cluster member stars located within the empirical instability strip are not RR Lyrae stars, and appear to be non-variable. They concluded that a *higher* He content, $Y=0.357$, is required to fully match the location of the RRc pulsators, but that a *lower* content, $Y=0.220$, is needed to match the location of the RRab stars.

Cruz Reyes et al. (2024) also drew attention to the fact that their catalogue does not exhibit the ‘Oosterhoff dichotomy’, viz. the division of Galactic globular clusters into two groups based on their average RRab periods. This is a long-standing problem in Galactic astrophysics which has been explicitly advanced by Gaia, and which I will look at further in essay 230.

Other studies have used the DR3 RR Lyrae sample to focus on specific globular clusters, including NGC 7006 (Arellano Ferro et al., 2023b), Palomar 2 (Arellano Ferro et al., 2023a), and NGC 1851 (Arellano Ferro et al., 2024).